

CONTRIBUTO TEORICO

Competenze professionali in materia di sostenibilità culturale. Un caso di studio nel territorio fiorentino.

Professional competences in the field of cultural sustainability. A case study in the Florence Region.

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ABSTRACT ITALIANO

Il contributo descrive un quadro teorico funzionale ad interpretare le competenze dei professionisti nel settore culturale nell'ambito della sostenibilità e delle sfide connesse al benessere e alla salute di individui e comunità. Le ipotesi teoriche dialogano con i primi risultati di una ricerca sviluppata in un progetto formativo con alcuni operatori culturali della Rete Tematica Museale "Musei di tutti" del territorio fiorentino, promotori di una iniziativa culturale in cui bambini e famiglie hanno co-creato un servizio educativo. La ricerca-azione ha stimolato processi di autovalutazione e di riflessività, migliorando le pratiche culturali e l'efficacia educativa. I risultati presentati delineano sia la necessità di una maggiore attenzione alle competenze di sostenibilità culturale dei mediatori al patrimonio per perseguire obiettivi di benessere e trasformazione sociale attraverso la cultura che il bisogno di un maggiore dibattito sul tema, ancora poco sviluppato.

ENGLISH ABSTRACT

The paper describes a functional theoretical framework for interpreting the competences of cultural practitioners in the context of sustainability and the new challenges related to the well-being and health of individuals and communities. The theoretical hypotheses presented are in dialogue with the first results of a research developed in the context of a training project with some cultural professionals of the thematic museum network "Museums for All" in Florence, which promoted the involvement of children and families in the co-creation of an educational offer. The research training carried out stimulated processes of self-assessment and reflexivity that improved cultural practises and pedagogical effectiveness. The research findings emphasise both the need to pay more attention to the cultural sustainability skills of cultural practitioners in order to pursue goals of well-being and social change through culture, and the need for greater debate on this still underdeveloped topic.

Introduction

New scientific evidence shows that the cultural sector and its professionals can contribute to overcoming several economic, social and political crises that prevail in some Western countries, including Italy, and are related to material and educational poverty, an ageing population, abstentionism, multiculturalism and the weakening of welfare systems (Maino, 2023). For this reason, increasing attention has been paid in recent years to the impact and potential benefits of culture, particularly cultural heritage.

This renewed interest stimulates interesting reflections on the training and acquisition of new and transversal competences (1) by professionals in this field.

In particular, numerous studies referring to the category of 'Second Welfare' (Maino & Ferrera, 2013) in Italy (articulated, e.g. in 'Cultural Welfare' or 'Community Welfare'), argue in favour of the need to reshape the relationships between the different social actors and increasingly see culture as a way to improve people's well-being and health and thus reduce the burden on health systems, promote participation and thus support citizenship and active ageing, improve social cohesion and the sense of cultural belonging as well as non-formal education and learning (Himdad et al., 2023; Gallou, 2022; Zbranca et al., 2022; Fancourt & Finn, 2019; Iwasaki, Messina & Hopper, 2018). As early as 2014, the WHO counted culture among the individual and social determinants of health, i.e. among the factors that, together with genetic predisposition and access to high-quality social and health services, can influence health status and life expectancy (Marmot, 2014).

Cultural fruition promotes capacitation (2) (Nussbaum, 2013; Sen, 2000) when a cognitive mobilisation develops in individuals (Foray, 2000) in which, in addition to the presence and transmission of information relating to traditional knowledge and cultural objects, the participation and intentionality of the subject to internalise new knowledge is also present. Once the learning process is activated by cultural experiences, the production of new knowledge and its long-term utilisation in different domains of existence is determined (Del Gobbo, 2007). In a process of continuous maintenance, the knowledge and skills that individuals possess promote and enable access, enjoyment and conscious utilisation of cultural heritage, creating new dynamic forms of cultural practises (Del Gobbo, Torlone & Galeotti, 2018). Through the cultural enjoyment of culture, the acquired skills (3) promote the ability to cope with psychological, social and physical challenges (Sansalone et al., 2023), which has a positive impact on overall levels of health and well-being. In addition, the skills developed through culture can promote the dynamic and creative utilisation of individual and collective resources to achieve goals and improve quality of life.

The role of cultural professionals in promoting well-being

Cultural professionals can play a crucial role in promoting cognitive access to culture by creating, in synergy with other territorial actors (from the cultural, social and health sectors), favourable contexts and modalities to promote participation, learning, empowerment and well-being. However, the competences of these actors are not always sufficient to tackle such far-reaching challenges.

In the literature and in the Italian panorama, it seems that the debate and reflection on professional competences in the cultural field is mainly found in the museum sector. The professionals working in the museum structures, regardless of the role they hold, should act in accordance with the fundamental principles of museums and their social function contained in the latest definition of ICOM, the International Council of Museums, of 2022:

A museum is a not-for-profit, permanent institution in the service of society that researches, collects, conserves, interprets and exhibits tangible and intangible heritage. Open to the public, accessible and inclusive, museums foster diversity and sustainability. They operate and communicate ethically, professionally and with the participation of

communities, offering varied experiences for education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing.

Among the key words of this definition, some are more "classical", i.e. the theme of accessibility (physical, cultural, economic, cognitive) and inclusion (respect for diversity); others are more innovative, such as the participation of communities in the interpretation and co-production of knowledge related to cultural heritage for the purpose of community and individual well-being. However, in this recent definition of the term museum, the word sustainability emerges above all, as it is clearly in continuity with the goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda - which was later also included in the agendas of international organisations such as UNESCO - which assigns cultural heritage an active and fundamental role in the areas of education, gender equality, sustainable development, inclusive territorial transformation and intercultural dialogue. It is necessary to include culture in the sustainability debate because it is equated with human actions and behaviours that are culturally embedded (Auclair & Fairclough, 2015; Ingold & Palsson, 2013). Furthermore, the study and exchange of cultural practises of resource management or service production can provide valuable insights into different sustainable ways of 'being-in-the-world' (Kohn, 2013).

Following the study by Soini and Dessein (2016), culture is considered in this paper both as a specific area of study of sustainability, as a capital (Bourdieu, 1980) that complements economic, social and environmental capital, and as a resource with a particular mediating role for human, social and economic futures. Consequently, culture is understood both as a process of intellectual, spiritual and aesthetic development (with its material and immaterial results) and as a transversal principle of 'being-in-the-world', as the relationship and meaning that one ascribes to one's living environment. A sustainable future (4) through culture refers to those processes in which the recognition, protection and transmission of cultural diversity and its expressions between generations and social groups make it possible to expand the choices of individuals and communities. Furthermore, sustainability through culture is understood as the promotion of territorial specificities in order to improve the overall quality of life. This is understood as the presence of diverse social relationships, territorial services and active participation in the democratic life of one's living environment (Atkinson et al., 2017).

In the ICOM definition of the museum, the requirement for ethical behaviour and the need for professionalism in the performance of museum functions are also important. The European Commission has been working for several years on the development and certification of qualifications for cultural professionals (see, for example, the following documents: European Commission & Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, 2018; *Voices of Culture*, 2017; European Commission, 2014). In the debate on professionalisation processes and competence frameworks aimed at cultural professionals, little space has been devoted to cultural sustainability competences, the theoretical foundations of which have been described above. This gap in the literature is probably due to three reasons. The first is related to the fact that culture has often been analysed in the context of social sustainability and rarely considered as a distinct and separate field. The second reason is related to the criticism of researchers who have tried to conceptualise

the relationship between sustainability and culture, which have often been seen as too broad and therefore ambiguous concepts. Finally, the third reason is related to the second, namely the lack of a solid conceptual framework for the relationship between these two issues (Soini & Dessein, 2016).

However, for some of the goals of the 2030 Agenda to be achieved, synergistic actions are needed from professionals and institutions in the cultural sector, which must both promote access to culture and work towards the goals of the new welfare paradigms, which, as already highlighted, relate to the well-being and health of individuals and communities through continuous, diverse and conscious cultural fruition in territories. Indeed, it is necessary for cultural organisations and their staff not to be content with providing a cultural service, but to challenge their methods and skills through training and non-formal learning processes to ensure that the experience in cultural places is "an opportunity for personal renewal, cultural hybridisation and the establishment of elastic and satisfying relationships" (Manzoli & Paltrinieri, 2021, p. 23).

Given the need for social promotion and the sustainable future of territories through culture, professionals working in this sector must acquire or perfect a series of competences with the aim of:

- valorise the skills of the individual;
- develop new skills and use them dynamically;
- create positive experiences of psycho-physical and social well-being that encourage audiences to experience and enjoy cultural activities;
- promote accessibility and continuous active participation, not only during specific cultural experiences;
- instil values of solidarity and inclusive citizenship and promote intergenerational dialogue;
- to promote and support new possible worlds and narratives through cultural heritage in terms of cultural creativity, multiculturalism and sustainability.

These objectives can be achieved if cultural professionals strengthen their transversal competences to meet the needs of place-making. Moreover, to have a significant impact on territories, cultural professionals increasingly need to know how to network with different local actors and professionals and analyse the territorial context of their activity in terms of its needs and potentials, applying pedagogical design competences for cultural and social sustainability goals (Mancaniello, Marone & Musaio, 2023).

The case study of the thematic museum network "Museums For All" of Florence and Fiesole

This research represents a first reflection on the need to develop cultural sustainability competences to meet new and emerging needs - of communities and individuals – such as well-being, social inclusion and cohesion and lifelong learning in territories. This hypothesis served as a guide for the interpretation of data related to a research-training project of the thematic museum network "Museums for All" of the Florence Region.

The experimental project "Museums from a children's perspective", promoted by the thematic museum network "Museums for All" in Florence and Fiesole, involved a very young primary school audience in the exploration of six museums, including in Florence the Palazzo Vecchio Museum, the Stefano Bardini Museum and the Innocenti Museum. In Fiesole, on the other hand, the Bandini Museum, the Civic Archaeological Museum and the Primo Conti Museum took part in the initiative. The cycle of four meetings that took place in the museums between October and December 2023 involved 48 young participants in the planning and implementation of preparatory activities for guided tours for peers scheduled for January-April 2024. In each museum institution, two cultural professionals were responsible for each group of at least five and a maximum of ten children. A total of 13 cultural professionals were involved in the project.

The thematic museum network project has three innovative aspects. Firstly, the involvement of the families of the Florence region, who, by participating in the initiative, gave their children the opportunity to take part in the museums' project activities, thus contributing to the provision of innovative and inclusive museum itineraries. Secondly, the children had the opportunity to actively enjoy the museum structure by freely observing and exploring the elements that most arouse their interest and curiosity. The third innovative aspect concerns the possibility of designing museum tours from the children's point of view in order to promote active learning processes.

The research training (5) described here is part of the thematic museum network project and aims to accompany cultural professionals in the monitoring and evaluation of activities in order to consolidate and develop their professional competences (Altieri, 2009; Palumbo & Torrigiani, 2009). The methods chosen for data collection were participant observation, questionnaire administration and the organisation of work tables. Both hermeneutic and outcome-orientated paradigms were used to interpret the collected data. In the first phase of the research, an observation sheet was created and used to investigate the actions of museum operators and children during cultural activities in museums. Simultaneously with the qualitative data collection, 3 types of questionnaires were developed and distributed, concerning the children's well-being and their trust in the museums, the involvement of the children's parents and their trust in the museum institutions, and the transversal and cultural sustainability competences of museum operators involved in the initiative. Between December 2023 and January 2024, 67 questionnaires were distributed, broken down as follows: 27 questionnaires to parents; 30 questionnaires to children; 10 questionnaires to cultural professionals.

Based on the data collected, it was possible to carry out a participatory reflection on the effectiveness of the project and the competences used, together with the cultural professionals and those responsible for the initiative, and to validate the information collected. An active exchange on the results achieved was encouraged at 3 work tables with the cultural professionals, which favoured both social (empowerment) and cognitive (learning) reinforcement (Bramanti & Odifreddi, 2006). The comprehensive and wide-ranging data collection using a mixed methods approach demonstrated a desire to infuse the pedagogical research process with a focus on social impact and to promote methods

that favour the comparison of different viewpoints and encourage the inclusion and dissemination of knowledge.

The results of the research and training project

The 3 work tables with the cultural professionals and the questionnaire given to them have achieved the objective of stimulating processes of self-assessment and reflexivity in order to promote innovation and improvement of cultural practises in terms of pedagogical effectiveness (Schultz, 1970). The areas of competence for cultural sustainability proposed in the questionnaires (6) for cultural professionals working in innovative projects such as the thematic museum network of Florence and Fiesole are:

- the ability to cultivate one's inner life, to develop a relationship with one's own thoughts, desires and values in order to be present, intentional and non-reactive when dealing with complexity;
- the ability to take different perspectives in order to make decisions;
- the ability to utilise available information by placing it in a broad context of social, cultural, environmental and economic sustainability;
- the ability to build, develop and foster collaborative relationships with co-creative goals;
- the ability to foster inclusive dialogue, genuinely consider the perspectives of others and adapt communication to different contexts and socio-cultural groups;
- the ability to break conventional patterns through creativity and to persevere in the face of uncertainty;
- the ability to maintain and communicate a sense of hope through a positive attitude and confidence in change;
- the ability to act decisively in line with their values and to persevere in the long term.

The results of the questionnaires show that most cultural professionals act in the spirit of cultural sustainability. In fact, all the cultural professionals interviewed had good intentions to work for the good of the whole and for goals linked to the well-being of the community through culture.

Competences related to networking, inclusive dialogue and breaking conventional patterns were more prevalent.

In contrast, when analysing the data, competences related to inner life and dialogue with sustainability were found to be lacking. Indeed, not all cultural professionals were able to utilise the cultural information available to them to make comprehensive, sustainability-related connections. Furthermore, some cultural professionals stated that they experience stress in their work and that they do not feel that their lifestyle respects the environment, their mental wellbeing and that of others. It is now well established in the literature that feelings of gratitude and connectedness to the world, as well as the skills associated with dialogue with one's inner life, have significant effects on work productivity, creativity, family and social reality, but also on income and health (Walsh, Boz & Lyubomirsky, 2023; Lyubomirsky, Sheldon & Schkade 2005). This suggests that more attention should probably be paid to the sustainability competences of cultural

professionals in order to pursue the goals of well-being and social transformation through culture.

Conclusions

The increasing complexity of today's working environments requires a strengthening of the competences of cultural professionals who are confronted with challenges related to their interdisciplinary and systemic design, planning and management skills. This need for renewal is based on the emerging needs in terms of well-being, sustainable future, lifelong learning, inclusion and social cohesion. The hypothesis put forward for the development of this paper refers to the fact that cultural professionals need to acquire and perfect competences related to cultural sustainability in order to achieve the goals of social promotion and the sustainable future of territories through culture. Sustainability competence refers to 'knowing how to do something', which is linked to both the relationship with one's inner life (one's values, self-perception and sense of belonging) and the ability to innovate through culture, to break conventional and habitual patterns, to enter into dialogue with the world around oneself and to persist in complexity and uncertainty.

The research-training activity described in this paper was useful for investigating the research hypothesis about the sustainability competences of cultural professionals. The evaluation and self-assessment of cultural practitioners proved to be an important learning opportunity to become aware of and act upon the competences required for structuring cultural pathways towards inclusion, well-being and non-formal learning. The outcome of the research training can be seen as an increase in social capital and thus knowledge potential in the network of museum institutions that designed the initiative. The expertise acquired through the research training project should then be made available in various ways to all employees of the participating museum institutions. It is hoped that the new knowledge gained will generate new forms of knowledge necessary to make cultural organisations resilient, i.e. able to anticipate and respond to societal changes and find a new balance for their function. These cultural organisations will be able to improve their ability to respond to differentiated and dynamic needs, thus determining possible side effects in terms of attractiveness and the ability to generate meaningful learning in a cultural welfare perspective.

Notes

- (1) Broadly defined as the totality of skills, knowledge, attitudes, motivations, values, and emotions that manifest themselves in a person's actions (OECD, 2002).
- (2) Understood as an extension of the possibility to determine one's present and future life through the development of new abilities.
- (3) The most frequently mentioned in the literature are: detachment, acceptance, problem-solving, self-development, psychological stress resistance, uncertainty tolerance, intercultural dialogue, adaptation, autonomy, introspection.
- (4) We prefer to use this term to distinguish ourselves from the concept of 'sustainable development', which has often been used as a synonym for sustainability since the

Brundtland Report 'Our Common Future' (1987). The term sustainability or sustainable future is intended to denote processes of cultural, economic and political change that are orientated towards sustainability and in which ecological and environmental problems are read in the context of other contemporary challenges (e.g. health or poverty); in which the human is no longer perceived as separate from the non-human; in which actions are both strongly based on shared values and oriented towards the collective good (Kassel, Rimanoczy, & Mitchell, 2016).

- (5) The project leader for the FORLILPSI department at the University of Florence is Prof. Giovanna Del Gobbo (giovanna.delgobbo@unifi.it).
- (6) The inner development goals framework (IDG: <https://innerdevelopmentgoals.org/>) was used as a reference for the construction of the items.

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